

INFLUENCE OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF CONCOMITANT STRABISMUS IN CHILDREN ON THE STATE OF BINOCULAR FUNCTIONS

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Relevance. Untimely treatment of concomitant strabismus, which is mainly a pathology of early childhood, becomes the main etiological and pathogenetic factors of low vision and visual disability from childhood. Its surgical treatment is one of the important stages of rehabilitation of patients with deviation, the quality of which significantly affects the restoration of binocular functions of the visual organ.

The aim of the work is to study the effectiveness of surgical treatment of concomitant convergent strabismus.

Material and methods. We conducted a retrospective analysis of the medical records of 96 children with concomitant convergent strabismus of both eyes who underwent inpatient surgical treatment in the eye diseases department of the multidisciplinary clinic of Samarkand State Medical University from 2020 to 2023. The age of the patients was 4-8 years (mean age 6.5 ± 0.55 years). There were 58 girls and 42 boys.

In 2-4 children, strabismus developed at birth; in 72 children, it developed between the ages of 2 and 5 years.

All patients underwent optical correction and orthoptic treatment in the preoperative period in the specialized kindergarten #79 for children in Samarkand, and also received treatment in outpatient clinics from an ophthalmologist at their place of residence. To form binocular vision, we used a synoptophore, amblyotrainer, muscle trainer, mosaic, stimulating the macular area with light, diploptics and pleoptics.

All patients with concomitant strabismus underwent a complete ophthalmological examination. The following research methods were used to assess the state of the functions of the visual organ and the refractive apparatus: determination of visual acuity using the Orlova and Golovin-Sivtsev tables, examination of the position of the eyes and the range of motion in 8 meridians, determination of the angle of strabismus according to Hirschberg using a Helmholtz mirror ophthalmoscope, as well as a synoptophore, examination of the refraction of the eyes with narrow and wide pupils using an autorefractometer, as well as by skiascopy: refraction was determined by cycloplegia by instillation of 1% atropine solution in an age-appropriate dosage to exclude side effects, and sometimes 1% tropicamide solution twice with an interval of 5 minutes in young children and using a PRK Supore autorefractometer (China), examination of the anterior segment, conducting media of the eye, and the fundus using a slit lamp (biomicroscopy). The condition of the fundus was studied using the methods of reverse and direct ophthalmoscopy, the nature of vision was determined using the 4-point Belostotsky-Friedman color test, and accommodation and convergence were determined using the accommodator convergenstrainer apparatus.

Functional treatment included courses of pleoptic, orthoptic and diploptic treatment, as well as courses of physiotherapy and electrical stimulation to influence the muscular apparatus of the eye, retina, optic nerve.

The course of treatment at the initial stage consisted of adequate spectacle correction and occlusion. Orthoptic treatment included: synoptophore, biviisotrainer, muscle trainer.

In all cases, the refraction in these patients was hypermetropic, from +0.75 D to +5.75 D (on average +2.75 D).

All children were consulted by a pediatric neurologist.

All patients were operated under general anesthesia, which produced recession of the internal rectus muscles of both eyes using a standard technique. To determine the volume of surgical intervention in concomitant convergent strabismus, the dosage scheme for surgical treatment of convergent strabismus proposed by E.S. Avetisov and H.I. Makhkamova was used as a basis.

Results and discussion. The patients were distributed according to the angle of strabismus: the angle of deviation of 10-15° was observed in 18 (18.75%) patients, 15-25° - in 54 (52.08%), the angle of deviation of 25-30° - in 24 (29.17%). Studying the immediate postoperative period, the angle of strabismus was corrected in 64 (66.7%) patients, they also had orthophoria. Patients with a residual angle of strabismus amounted to 24 (25%), they had a hypoeffect. Of these, in 8 cases there was a hypereffect, that is, secondary divergent strabismus was observed.

With a deviation angle of 10-25° according to Hirschberg, strabismus was eliminated in 85% of cases. With a deviation angle of more than 25°, the effect of the treatment significantly decreased, that is, the symmetrical position of the eye occurs in 60% of cases, in other cases it significantly improves, that is, the angle of strabismus decreases, but the hypoeffect remains.

It should be noted that if strabismus treatment is started at preschool age, the effect of the treatment will be much better than that of treatment started at school age. The number of patients who started treatment at the age of 3-5 years is 80%. With early development of strabismus (up to one year), the cosmetic effect of the treatment is very low and is 15-20%. Among children operated at the age of 5 to 7 years, bifoveal fusion and binocular vision significantly improved, and in children over 8 years of age, bifoveal fusion was not observed in any, despite vigorous orthoptic exercises. At the same time, with strabismus for 9 years, symmetrical position of the eyes was observed in 15% of the patients we examined.

Conclusions: Thus, the effect of surgical treatment on the state of binocular functions in 96 patients with concomitant strabismus, operated on at the age of 4-8 years, was studied. The results indicate high efficiency of this treatment in patients of early and preschool age: deviation was completely eliminated in 80% of operated patients. A positive effect of early surgical intervention on binocular sensory functions was also noted - this was manifested by the elimination of the phenomenon of functional inhibition in 65% of patients and a significant increase in the number of patients (from 10 to 40%) with the phenomenon of diplopia.

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